

Tree, a Boon

(Original poem in Tamil by the poet Dr. Balabarathi, translated by M. Vinoth Kumar)

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As sky and earth above and below- You
grew up as a sap on the earth!
You got the rain from the clouds – Then
grew up and said, “I am a Plant”
You get the roots as legs – Then
stand stood and said, “I am a tree”!
You stand stood and bear the sunshine on your head – And
gave aromatic chillness under your shade!
To the lives sing on you like me
gave shelter to the cuckoo and the eagle – Then
you stand still as big tree!
To chill your mother’s dried womb – By stopping
the rivers dry you gave the rain.
As my raising country be heightened – You also
flourished as a philosophy.

Acknowledgement: This poem evinces the source of life and dearness of nature in the poet’s heart and is a dedication to him.